

Task 3.1 Establish or improve sentinel-based electronic surveillance of serious infectious diseases or syndromes from hospitals in participating Member States

Infectious disease surveillance in Dutch hospitals

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Executive summary

This report by the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) presents the results of our pilot study in the Netherlands, part of task 3.1 of Workpackage 3 (WP3) Hospital surveillance in UNITED4surveillance.

After the COVID-19 pandemic, it has become even more apparent that strengthening our infectious disease surveillance in Dutch hospitals is urgently warranted to be better prepared for cross-border health threats. Despite a solid foundation in healthcare-associated infection and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) surveillance, the Netherlands faced multifactorial challenges in establishing robust sentinel severe acute respiratory infections (SARI) surveillance over the past decade. With the expiration of ad-hoc COVID-19 crisis regulation, COVID-19 and associated surveillance systems ceased to exist. However, with changing attitudes and increased perceived value of public health surveillance after the COVID-19 pandemic in key stakeholders, now is the time to establish sustainable SARI surveillance. Therefore, this pilot study aims to identify the minimal requirements for a robust and sustainable SARI surveillance system according to key stakeholders in the Netherlands. These pilot study's results may facilitate establishing robust and sustainable SARI surveillance in the Netherlands in the near future.

The objectives of our pilot study are the following:

- identify the most relevant stakeholders for SARI surveillance in the Netherlands;
- explore the relative position, the degree of influence, interest, and goals of each stakeholder with regard to SARI surveillance;
- define the preferred requirements for a SARI surveillance system in order to be valuable and feasible for stakeholders;
- map which data are already available for stakeholders that could be used for a future or existing surveillance system;
- identify current practices and most relevant barriers and facilitators according to stakeholders in achieving a robust and sustainable national SARI surveillance system.

These objectives are met by delivering i) a stakeholder analysis report on hospital surveillance; ii) a scientific article based on semi-structured interviews with key Dutch stakeholders on hospital surveillance; and iii) a blueprint for SARI surveillance in the Netherlands. The objective “mapping available data already available to stakeholders”

will not be addressed separately, due to the limited new input from external stakeholders during semi-structured interviews. However, we have undertaken additional pilot initiatives beyond our initial pilot plan, such as implementing a communication strategy plan for SARI surveillance and retrospective analysis of intensive care unit (ICU) scoring system (APACHE) for potential use in hospital surveillance, other than SARI.

In conclusion, our pilot study WP3 task 3.1 contributes to establishing and improving (sentinel) infectious disease surveillance in hospitals in the Netherlands. The main take-aways of our pilot study are described below:

A comprehensive understanding of stakeholders and their roles in SARI surveillance is essential for building a robust SARI surveillance system

Our stakeholder analysis ([appendix 1](#)) provides an updated and comprehensive overview of all relevant stakeholders with their specific roles (decision makers, suppliers, end-users and influencers) in SARI surveillance in the Netherlands since the end of the COVID-19 pandemic. This results in valuable insights, such as: i) newly identified stakeholders, ii) multiple stakeholders having more than one role, and iii) the possibility of clustering stakeholders in groups based on power of influence and interest. This is essential information for determining how and where to inform, involve and/or collaborate with stakeholders for establishing or maintaining SARI surveillance now or in the future. A force field analysis offers additional insights into personal attitudes, involvement, influence, and relationships regarding SARI surveillance, but details are confidential and will not be disclosed. However, the results of both analyses equally contributed to developing our communication strategy plan for SARI surveillance in the Netherlands. This communication strategy plan, an additional key result of our pilot study, will guide future communication with stakeholders in the field of SARI surveillance. This communication strategy plan will be a dynamic document requiring periodic updates.

Barriers, facilitators, and recommendations identified by Dutch hospitals offer valuable insights for enhancing hospital surveillance

The conducted semi-structured interviews ([appendix 2](#)) on infectious disease surveillance in hospitals offer essential insights in the experienced barriers, facilitators, and wishes from the perspective of stakeholders in the hospital setting. The most quoted barriers by these participants are: i) the unclear stakeholder roles and

responsibilities; ii) the different interpretation of General Data Protection Regulation; and iii) having insufficient resources and capacity. The most relevant facilitators for SARI surveillance according to participants are: i) obtaining clinically relevant and actionable data; ii) mutually beneficial collaboration; and iii) having sufficient support. Participants recommend three key actions to establish or maintain robust infectious disease surveillance in hospitals. The current adjustment of the Public Health Act (Wpg) in the Netherlands could contribute to this. Firstly, public health institutes should focus on clinically relevant actionable surveillance data that impact patient clinical care. Secondly, all stakeholders should collaboratively define roles and responsibilities in hospital surveillance more clearly. Finally, public health institutes should benefit from the innovative qualities of hospitals and microbiology laboratories to a greater extent.

A blueprint for SARI surveillance in the Netherlands advances by implementing two promising scenarios

We provide a blueprint ([appendix 3](#)) based on the most promising scenarios for establishing SARI surveillance in the Netherlands. The two most promising scenarios for establishing SARI surveillance currently in Q4 2024 in the Netherlands are: 1) using case-based data streams on SARI based on financial claim codes (DBC) from the Dutch Hospital Database (DHD) complemented with laboratory outcomes; and 2) using aggregated data streams on SARI based severity-of-disease classification system (APACHE) from the National Intensive Care Evaluation Registry (NICE). This blueprint may guide key stakeholders, like hospitals and microbiological laboratories, in implementing SARI surveillance in collaboration with the RIVM. In addition, it informs external stakeholders, such as the Dutch Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport, about the current status and rollout plans of these two scenarios for SARI surveillance. We expect that both scenarios are operational in 2025, after which an evaluation will determine in 2026 whether both data streams are necessary for representative SARI surveillance in the Netherlands.

Additional pilot initiatives have been undertaken

Our retrospective analysis of ICU data for other syndromes than SARI ([appendix 4](#)) offers insights that could potentially strengthen infectious disease surveillance in Dutch hospitals and thereby improving preparedness for cross-border health threats. To this end, we evaluated the usefulness of APACHE diagnoses codes for the 'gastrointestinal infections' syndrome using the NICE registry during a 10-year period. The preliminary results indicate a lack of added value with regard to timeliness and completeness of the

data compared to the already existing gastrointestinal and zoonosis surveillance systems in the Netherlands. However, we aim to retrospectively explore additional infectious disease syndromes, including healthcare-associated infections and neuro-infectious syndromes, using the NICE registry after the pilot ends.

Appendix 1. Stakeholder analysis

Background

Need for SARI surveillance

The need for surveillance of Severe Acute Respiratory Infections (SARI) became apparent after the influenza A(H1N1) pandemic in 2009, after which the World Health Organization (WHO) recommended SARI surveillance in every country [1]. While progress was made in establishing SARI surveillance in several countries, a robust and sustainable SARI surveillance system was established only in a limited number of countries [2, 3]. The COVID-19 pandemic has again shown the urgent need for robust and sustainable SARI data that can serve multiple purposes, such as providing input for public health surveillance, individual patient care, hospital bed capacity planning, and healthcare policy [4].

SARI surveillance in the Netherlands

In the last decade, the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) has initiated several projects to set up a robust and sustainable SARI surveillance system in the Netherlands [5]. For instance, one of these projects aims to retrieve real-time data on SARI from the quality-of-care registry of intensive care units (ICUs) [6], while another project aims to pilot sentinel SARI surveillance [7]. So far, these initiatives have shown mixed results in achieving this goal. Reasons for not yet achieving a sustainable SARI surveillance system in the Netherlands are multifactorial and range from increased registration burden, lack of fully automated surveillance systems, different appreciation of the value of epidemiological surveillance data, to a large diverse group of stakeholders [3]. However, it is essential that we overcome these barriers and find common ground among stakeholders to achieve a robust SARI surveillance system, to be better prepared for future health threats.

This pilot

In this pilot study, we aim to map the stakeholders of SARI surveillance in the Netherlands to gain a comprehensive overview of the involved stakeholders with their roles and level of influence. These in-depth insights into stakeholders are important for establishing a robust, automated, and sustainable SARI surveillance system in the future.

Methods

Design

This report is part of a pilot study within the hospital surveillance (Work Package 3) of the Joint Action UNITED4Surveillance, consisting of 24 EU Member States. The aim of UNITED4Surveillance is to contribute to improving preparedness against cross-border health threats in Europe, by strengthening infectious disease surveillance systems on both national and European levels [8].

Definition of stakeholder

A stakeholder can be defined as an individual or a group that has an interest or a share in a project or organization [9]. For this stakeholder analysis, we tailored this definition to individuals, groups, and organizations that have an interest or a share in SARI surveillance in the Netherlands. When organizations had similar or overlapping activities in SARI surveillance, we grouped them together in one stakeholder cluster.

Role matrix

The stakeholder analysis was performed in two work group sessions. The first session was performed by a team of four senior epidemiologists and one infectious disease specialist from the RIVM. Stakeholders were identified during a brainstorming session with these experts. Stakeholders were subsequently placed in the role matrix based on their role(s) in SARI surveillance in the Netherlands, being:

- i) supplier of knowledge, resources, or data for SARI surveillance
- ii) end user of the outcomes of SARI surveillance
- iii) decision maker regarding the process and system of SARI surveillance
- iv) influencer of decisions and actions regarding the process and final SARI surveillance system

In case of disagreement, discussion was continued until a unanimous decision was reached.

Mendelow's matrix

In the second work group session, a power-interest matrix was used to characterize the previously identified stakeholders. In this matrix analysis, "power" was defined as the degree of power of influence to enable or oppose the establishment of SARI surveillance in the Netherlands, and "interest" as the level of interest and attitude of stakeholders towards SARI surveillance in the Netherlands. Stakeholders were characterized by their

degree of power of influence (i.e., low, middle, or high) and level of interest (i.e., low, middle, or high), and positioned in a Mendelow's matrix [10] during a brainstorming session with experts from the RIVM. This second session of the stakeholder analysis was performed by a team of five experts in hospital surveillance and public health, consisting of two infectious disease specialists, one medical microbiologist, and two senior epidemiologists. In case of disagreement within the team on the power and/or interest of a stakeholder, discussion was continued until consensus was reached.

Stakeholder details and analysis

Additionally, stakeholder representatives were identified on an individual level. The results of this part of the study, e.g. name and contact details, will not be included in this report due to privacy reasons. Descriptive analyses were used to describe the outcomes of the role matrix and Mendelow's matrix, using absolute numbers and proportions.

Results

Role matrix

Based on the results from the stakeholder analysis, we identified 29 stakeholders ([Supplementary material 1](#)). While some stakeholders were identified on organizational level (e.g. the Data Protection Authority (AP), the European Commission (EC)), others were clustered on a more overarching level, such as 'hospital groups' (e.g. the Dutch Federation of University Medical Centres (NFU), the Dutch Association of Hospitals (NVZ)), and 'research institutes'. Notably, the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) is shown separately on organizational level, despite belonging to the cluster 'research institutes', because the RIVM is the primary end user of this stakeholder analysis.

Stakeholders were positioned as having one or more of the following roles: suppliers (n=8/29), decision-makers (n=2/29), end users (n=16/29), and influencers (n=16/29) ([Table 1](#)). While most stakeholders were identified as having a single role in SARI surveillance (18/29), multiple stakeholders were identified as having two or more roles (n=11/29). Most positions were held by the Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sports (VWS) and the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), being both decision-maker, influencer, and end user. Notably, while VWS and RIVM both hold the role of decision maker regarding SARI surveillance, it occurs on distinct levels. The decisions on the policy for SARI surveillance are made by VWS, while decisions on the system for SARI surveillance are made by the RIVM. Additionally, the position of both

end user and influencer was held by the EC, European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC), Health Council (GR), National Acute Care Network (LNAZ), and the World Health Organization (WHO). Also, two positions were held by Dutch Hospital Data and National Intensive Care Evaluation (DHD and NICE, i.e. influencer and supplier), and hospitals and hospital groups (i.e. suppliers and end users).

Table 1. Role matrix of stakeholders for SARI surveillance in the Netherlands

End Users	Influencers
Citizens	Data Protection Authority (AP)
European Commission / European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control / World Health Organization (EC / ECDC / WHO)	Dutch Association of Hospitals (NVZ)
Municipal Health Services (GGD)	Dutch Competence Centre for Electronic Exchange of Health and Care Information (Nictiz)
Municipal Health Services & Medical Assistance Organizations in the Region (GGD GHOR)	Dutch Healthcare Authority (NZa)
Health Council (GR)	Dutch Hospital Data / National Intensive Care Evaluation (DHD / NICE)
Hospitals / Hospital groups	National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM)
Knowledge centres	European Commission / European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control / World Health Organization (EC / ECDC / WHO)
National Acute Care Network (LNAZ)	Health Council (GR)
Media	Inspection of Healthcare and Youth (IGJ)
Pharmaceutical companies	Medical professional associations
Research institutes	Ministry of Health, Wellbeing and Sports (VWS)
National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM)	National Acute Care Network (LNAZ)
Ministry of Health, Wellbeing and Sports (VWS)	The Dutch Federation of University Medical Centres (NFU)
Suppliers	Decision makers
Dutch Hospital Data (DHD)	National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM)
Electronic health record supplier	Ministry of Health, Wellbeing and Sports (VWS)
External ICT companies	
Hospitals / Hospital groups	
Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) supplier	
Medical Microbiology (MMB) laboratories	
National Intensive Care Evaluation (NICE)	

Note. See [supplementary material 1](#) for a more detailed stakeholders description.

Mendelow’s matrix

Several of the identified stakeholders were clustered based on common characteristics, including similar organizational roles, interests, and power of influence in SARI surveillance in the Netherlands. This resulted in 23 identified stakeholder groups, which were placed in Mendelow's matrix [11] (Figure 1). Whereas almost half of the stakeholders were identified as stakeholders with high power (n=10/23), less than a quarter were identified as stakeholders with high interest (n=5/23). RIVM and VWS were identified as stakeholders with both the highest power and interest. The segment with high power with medium interest contained most stakeholders (n=5/23).

Figure 1. Mendelow’s matrix of SARI surveillance in the Netherlands

Note 1. AP = Data Protection Authority. DHD = Dutch Hospital Data. EHR = Electronic Health Record. EC = European Commission. ECDC = European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control. GGD = Municipal Health Services. GGD GHOR = Municipal Health Services & Medical Assistance Organizations in the Region. GR = Health Council. ICT = Information and Communication Technology. IGJ = Inspection of Healthcare and Youth. LIMS = Laboratory Information Management System. LNAZ = National Acute Care Network. MMB = Medical microbiology. Nictiz = Dutch Competence Centre for Electronic Exchange of Health and Care

Information. NICE = National Intensive Care Evaluation. NZa = Dutch Healthcare Authority. RIVM = National Institute for Public Health and the Environment. WHO = World Health Organization.

Note 2. See [supplementary material 1](#) for a more detailed description of the stakeholders.

Note 3. Overlying stakeholder text boxes are positioned in the middle of the cluster.

Discussion

Principal findings

This stakeholder analysis resulted in an overview of the field of stakeholders and their roles in SARI surveillance in the Netherlands. Firstly, while stakeholders like RIVM and VWS were already known to play an influential role in SARI surveillance in the Netherlands, a large group of other stakeholders and their roles were additionally identified. Secondly, when looking into the roles of each stakeholder in SARI surveillance, we found that multiple stakeholders held more than one role. Lastly, many stakeholders were found to be clustered in groups, when looking at their power of influence and interest in SARI surveillance. These are valuable insights, as they improve understanding about which stakeholders to involve and consider when establishing a robust and sustainable SARI surveillance in the Netherlands. To our knowledge, no published studies using stakeholder analysis in the field of SARI surveillance were previously conducted. Therefore, we could not compare our findings with other studies.

Strengths and limitations

A strength of this research is that we adjusted the composition of the expert teams of the two stakeholder analysis sessions based on a desired level of expertise. By including two senior epidemiologists in the first session, and a microbiologist and one more infectious disease specialist in the second session for more in depth hospital knowledge, more specialized knowledge was obtained during the sessions. Possibly, this resulted in a more robust stakeholder analysis.

A limitation of our stakeholder analysis is that it was performed only by researchers from the RIVM, and no external stakeholders were involved. This may have led to a restricted range of perspectives and information, potentially leading to less representative results.

Recommendations and future perspectives

Include external stakeholder perspectives

While identifying stakeholders is critical to ensure stakeholders are not overlooked [12-14], this pilot study did not identify stakeholder relationships yet. The latter should include the viewpoints, understandings, and attitudes of the relevant stakeholders with regard to SARI surveillance [12]. To accomplish this, we recommend involving external

stakeholders in the stakeholder analysis by e.g., performing interviews, focus group interviews, and/or informal group discussions. These activities potentially result in timely identification of barriers and opportunities [12].

Stakeholder communication strategy

Additionally, stakeholder involvement may result in a more in-depth knowledge of how to communicate with different stakeholders and keep everyone involved in the process up to date [9]. Therefore, we recommend creating a stakeholder communication plan, based on the current findings and input from stakeholders. This can potentially be used to communicate with stakeholders more effectively, identify areas of conflict and agreement and may result in a greater chance of success in establishing and/or maintaining a SARI surveillance system in the Netherlands.

Other hospital surveillance systems

For other hospital surveillance systems of the RIVM, such as surveillance of hospital-acquired infections [15], stakeholder analysis were also performed for internal use. However, looking into the stakeholders of different hospital surveillance systems in the Netherlands may reveal overlapping stakeholders. This process is currently ongoing and could potentially facilitate a more targeted approach towards stakeholders by the RIVM.

Conclusion

This study provides a current overview of the stakeholders of SARI surveillance in the Netherlands, in which stakeholders are identified, categorized, and differentiated based on their degree of power and interest. In addition, we identified a large stakeholder group involved in SARI surveillance, which could also be grouped based on their role, level of power of influence and level of interest. These findings, together with the recommendation to apply the stakeholder analysis for a more targeted stakeholder communication strategy, could contribute to establishing a robust SARI surveillance system in the Netherlands in the future.

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Supplementary material 1.

Table S1. Overview of stakeholders

Stakeholder	Involvement in the issue	Consist of	Meaning of abbreviation
Citizens	Receiving information about the status of infectious diseases		
Data Protection Authority (AP)	Protection of data and privacy		
DHD	Collecting data for infectious disease status on the intensive care		Dutch Hospital Data
EC	Coordinating and supporting efforts to monitor and infectious diseases across the European Union		European Commission
ECDC	Collecting and analyzing data on infectious diseases across Europe		European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
Electronic health record supplier	Facilitating platform for hospitals to collect, store and analyze patient data	<i>ChipSoft</i>	
		<i>Epic</i>	
		<i>Itemedical</i>	
		<i>Philips</i>	
		<i>Nexus</i>	
External ICT companies	Providing hospitals with the right platform to collect patient data		
GGD GHOR	Collecting and analyzing data on infectious diseases		Municipal Health Services & Medical Assistance Organizations in the Region
GGD	Collecting and analyzing data on infectious diseases		Municipal Health Services
GR	Advising the government on how to prevent and control infectious diseases		Health Council

	Coordinating and sharing data between member hospitals	<i>STZ</i>	Collaborating Top Clinical Hospitals
		<i>Santeon</i>	
		<i>Mprove</i>	
		<i>NFU</i>	The Dutch Federation of University Medical Centres
		<i>NVZ</i>	Dutch Association of Hospitals
Hospital groups		<i>Intensivist</i>	
Hospitals	Collecting data for infectious disease status		
IGJ	Monitoring quality and safety of healthcare in the Netherlands		Inspection of Healthcare and Youth
Knowledge centre	Sharing knowledge about (future) infectious diseases, i.e. Pandemic Disaster & Preparedness Centre (PDPC)		
LIMS supplier	Facilitating platform for hospitals to manage and track patient laboratory data		Laboratory Information Management System
LNAZ	Monitoring of the capacity and availability of hospital beds in the Netherlands		National acute care network
Media	May report on infectious disease outbreaks and other health-related news		
	Providing guidance and expertise in management and prevention of outbreaks	<i>FMS</i>	Federation of Medical Specialists
		<i>NIV</i>	Dutch Internists Association
		<i>NVMM</i>	Dutch Association for Medical Microbiology
Medical professional associations		<i>NVALT</i>	Dutch Association for Physicians for

			Pulmonary Diseases and Tuberculosis
		<i>NVII</i>	Dutch Association of Internist-Infectediologists
		<i>NVIC</i>	Dutch association of Intensive Care
		<i>NVK</i>	Dutch Association of Pediatrics
MMB laboratories	Analyzing and creating patient lab data, including VVML (Association of Medical Microbiological Laboratories)		
NICE	Collecting data for infectious disease status on the intensive care		National Intensive Care Evaluation
Nictiz	Supporting data sharing, collecting and analysis for surveillance		Dutch competence centre for electronic exchange of health and care information
NZa	Monitoring health care and advising VWS		Dutch healthcare authority
Pharmaceutical companies	Receive information about the status of infectious diseases		
Research institutes	Creating and sharing knowledge about infectious diseases, i.e. Nivel		
RIVM (National Institute for Public Health and the Environment)	Monitoring and controlling infectious diseases in the Netherlands, in line with its mandate to protect and improve public health	<i>EPI</i>	Centre for Epidemiology and Surveillance of infectious Diseases
		<i>LCI</i>	National Coordination Communicable Disease Control
		<i>DVP</i>	Centre Vaccine Supply and Prevention Programs Service
		<i>LFI</i>	National Functionality for Upscaling Infectious Disease Control
		<i>IDS</i>	The Centre for Infectious Disease Research, Diagnostics and Laboratory Surveillance

	Coordinating and overseeing public health in the Netherlands	<i>Directorate of Legislation and Legal Affairs</i>	Supporting policy in the areas of legislation, law enforcement and legal procedures
		<i>Directorate of Infectious Disease Policy</i>	Protecting against consequences of infectious diseases
		<i>Directorate of Public Health</i>	Promoting general health, prevention of diseases, medical ethics and managing crises and disasters
VWS (Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sports)		<i>Directorate of Curative Care</i>	Developing, implementing, and evaluating policy in curative care
WHO	Guiding and supporting efforts to monitor and infectious diseases worldwide		World Health Organization

Appendix 2. Semi-structured interviews

Background

The COVID-19 pandemic has shown the urgent need for robust and sustainable hospital data that can serve multiple purposes, such as providing input for public health surveillance, individual patient care, hospital bed capacity planning, and healthcare policy. Over the last decade, the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) has initiated several attempts to set up a severe acute respiratory infections (SARI) surveillance system in the Netherlands [1], including SARI surveillance based on the data from a quality-of-care registry in intensive care units (ICUs) [2] and SARI surveillance based on financial claim codes [3]. Reasons for not achieving a sustainable SARI surveillance system yet are multifactorial and range from high registration burden, lack of fully automated and timely data transfer, a large diverse group of stakeholders, and varying appreciation of the value of epidemiological surveillance data [4]. However, the COVID-19 pandemic might have shifted the opinion of stakeholders regarding the value of infectious disease surveillance based on hospital data and their level of engagement in pandemic preparedness. Evaluating the gaps and needs with regard to hospital surveillance from the perspective of the most relevant stakeholders is needed. Therefore, we performed qualitative research using semi-structured interviews to provide an overview of barriers, facilitators, and preferred requirements for an infectious disease surveillance system in hospitals to be valuable and feasible from a hospital perspective.

Methods

Design

We conducted semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders regarding infectious disease surveillance in hospitals in the Netherlands. This qualitative research is part of a Dutch pilot study within a larger EU4Health Project, UNITED4Surveillance (Work package 3: hospital surveillance) [5]. The Joint Action UNITED4Surveillance (project period 2023-2026), consisting of 24 Member States, aims to strengthen infectious disease surveillance for improved preparedness against cross-border health threats in Europe [6].

Participants

The most relevant stakeholder groups (i.e., organizations and their representatives) with moderate to high influence and interest regarding hospital surveillance were identified in a stakeholder analysis that was performed prior to the current study. Within these stakeholder groups we used a purposive sampling approach to select key stakeholders

based on variation in job position, type of hospital (academic/general), and/or medical specialty focus. These stakeholders included clinical staff from different departments in hospitals, clinical staff from microbiological laboratories, members of hospital boards, policy officers from different departments within the Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport, and representatives from medical specialist associations in the Netherlands. The selected key stakeholders were invited by email to participate in a semi-structured interview on infectious disease surveillance in hospitals. Prior to the interview, all participants received an information letter about the interview study and an informed consent form. Written informed consent was obtained for all participants and will be securely stored at the RIVM for a period of 10 years.

Interviews

The interviews took place using videoconferencing from October 2023 through January 2024. A semi-structured interview guide was established with a predefined topic list, which was developed by the authors and two additional researchers from the Centre for Infectious Disease Epidemiology and Surveillance of the RIVM (for details see [Supplementary material 2](#)). The guide included open-ended questions on functional infectious disease surveillance systems in hospitals, existing barriers and facilitating factors, available databases/sets/standards for potential use, and the preferred requirements for hospital surveillance from a hospital perspective. The interviews were conducted in Dutch by two RIVM researchers; a senior epidemiologist (TB) and an infectious disease specialist (SDM). The role of interviewer or note taker was divided prior to each interview between these two researchers. The interview duration was approximately 45 minutes, ranging from a half hour to one hour. On two occasions out of fourteen interviews, group interviews took place on specific request by the invited stakeholder group. All other interviews were held with a single participant. All interviews were video-recorded and subsequently converted into audio files to facilitate anonymous transcription by an external company (Uitgetypt.nl). The verbatim transcripts were shared with participants for checking. The interview quotations used for this article were translated from Dutch to English by the first RIVM researcher and the translation was checked by the second RIVM researcher.

Analysis

The two interviewers independently identified and coded segments within each transcript using the qualitative data analysis software (MAXQDA, version 24.1.0). Codes close to the topic list were used as a starting point for overarching themes and for the underlying (sub)themes codes were used as they emerged from the data. If the coding of the researchers diverged, the assessment was re-evaluated to reach consensus. Using

a thematic analytic approach, we identified common themes and their associations. When sufficient data saturation was reached to draw conclusions from thematic analysis, i.e., no more new codes were identified, qualitative data collection was stopped.

Results

We conducted fourteen interviews. The professions of the participants in interviews were medical microbiologists, infectious disease specialists, intensivist, elderly care physician, hospital board director, clinical epidemiologist, and infectious disease pediatricians. The participants of the first group interview included three policy officers: one in hospital care, one in long-term care, and one in COVID-19. A policy officer and medical microbiologist took part in the second group interview ([Table 2](#)).

Table 2. Characteristics of participants in semi-structured interviews

Professional background	Workplace	Participants (n)
Internist-intensivist	General hospital	1
Internist-infectiologist	Academic hospital	1
	General hospital	1
Medical microbiologist	Academic hospital	4
	General hospital	2
Pediatrician	Academic hospital	2
Internist-geriatric medicine	General hospital	1
Clinical epidemiologist	Academic hospital	1
Policy officer	Regional laboratory	1
	Municipal health service	
Policy officer	Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport	3
Total		17

Operational infectious disease surveillance systems in hospitals

In general, the participants mostly discussed three large groups of operational infectious disease surveillance systems in hospitals: i) antimicrobial resistance (AMR) surveillance systems; ii) healthcare-associated infection surveillance systems; and iii) severe acute respiratory infections (SARI) surveillance systems. Antimicrobial resistance surveillance systems were often described by participants in relation to outbreak detection. The participants described healthcare-associated infection surveillance systems, such as postoperative wound and line infections, more frequently in relation to ‘infection prevention control’ and ‘quality-of-care’. In general, most participants perceived AMR surveillance and healthcare-associated infection surveillance (e.g., line infection and postoperative wound infection) [7] as useful and clinically relevant. The operational

respiratory infections surveillance systems in hospitals discussed by the participants were characterized by their large diversity, ranging from (inter)personal observations to fully automated, (near) real-time laboratory surveillance of respiratory pathogens. The perceived value of a future SARI surveillance system in their hospital by hospital-based-participants is mixed. Some participants indicated that the value of a future SARI surveillance system might be regarded as less relevant by medical specialties other than medical microbiology or infectious disease. Other participants in the hospital setting underlined the relevance of a robust SARI surveillance system, particularly during outbreaks.

Barriers

Unclear stakeholder roles and responsibilities

A common theme apparent from the interviews was the unclear or passive role of hospitals in public health surveillance ([Table 3](#)).

Table 3. Perceived facilitators and barriers for establishing robust infectious disease surveillance in Dutch hospitals

Barriers	Description
Legal constraints	Constraints on sharing and linking of hospital data under the General Data Protection Regulation
Technical constraints	Information communication technology constraints on linking, extracting, and sharing hospital data using electronic patient records, laboratory information management systems, and other internal or external databases
Capacity constraints	Constraints on staff capacity (medical staff, data managers, information communication experts) or materials (computers, software, digital platforms)
Financial constraints	Limitation on financial budget specifically allocated to infectious disease surveillance in hospitals
Lack of support	Low support and/or prioritization of infectious disease surveillance activities from multiple levels in the hospital setting
High registration burden	The high registration burden of infectious disease surveillance tasks due to lack or insufficient automatization
Unclear role division	Uncertainty of role division between stakeholders involved in infectious disease surveillance in the hospital setting
Lack of uniformity	Lack of uniformity in i) aim and objectives of infectious disease surveillance in hospitals between stakeholder groups; ii) coding of infectious diseases and/or syndromes; iii) information communication technology standards
Lack of efficiency	Output of infectious disease surveillance has no or insufficient clinical consequences for patientcare in daily practice

Knowledge gap	Insufficient knowledge on trends of infectious diseases and/or syndromes in hospitalized patients
Facilitators	Description
Collaboration	Collaboration between stakeholders on multiple levels with regard to infectious disease surveillance in hospitals
Sufficient support	Sufficient support and/or prioritization of infectious disease surveillance activities on multiple levels in the hospital setting
Data for action	Output of infectious disease surveillance has clinical consequences for patientcare in daily practice
Clear division of roles and tasks	A clear role and task description between stakeholders in infectious disease surveillance in the hospital setting
Public health interest	Infectious disease surveillance in hospitals, especially during outbreaks, which has demonstrable impact on public health
Innovation	The adaption of innovative technologies or methods that contribute to both infectious disease surveillance and clinical care
Low registration burden	The low registration burden of infectious disease surveillance activities due to a fully automated, digitalized, and integrated surveillance system

Several medical specialists expressed that they do not feel that hospitals have a distinct role and/or responsibility in public health surveillance. Although most participants found it important to be notified if an infectious disease outbreak with an impact on hospital care is detected:

“If there is something unusual we need to know, I assume we will be told. There are plenty of channels where you can find that information. So if it is necessary, that it is there. Of course, it is also a matter of trust. I assume - I think most doctors have this confidence - that the RIVM will report issues if there is something noteworthy.” (participant 1)

Insight in the current role, responsibilities, and perceived urgency of having a robust respiratory surveillance in place in hospitals, was reflected by the one participant as follows:

“Every year we know that respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) will come again, and it is the same question every year: is it more? Are we testing more now? How bad is it now? [...] Then I will go on the news and say: we are on the edge of being overwhelmed, but we will still manage [...] How many admissions there really are and whether it is worse than last year we don’t know. With the Mycoplasma outbreak, the mega Mycoplasma outbreak that we had, we only found out about it, when [hospital capacity] was exceeded.” (participant 13)

Other participants expressed their willingness to actively participate in infectious disease surveillance with a broader public health scope in hospitals, but encountered problems to effectuate this. This was due to a lack of clear role description and a supportive legal framework.

“But it's things like that, and rules, that you run into. That there should be a vision about this: what is public health? And what is the role of hospitals in public health? And define that we in fact do have a role. Now it is so strictly separated that we have no role. And that means you can't do anything.” (participant 14)

Different Interpretation of General Data Protection Regulation

Dealing with different interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in relation to infectious disease surveillance in hospitals was regarded by many participants as a major challenge. Several participants mentioned the tendency of local privacy officers in hospitals to be conservative and nonuniform in their advice to medical specialists about sharing data for public health reasons. According to these participants this involves both sharing and linking patient- and/or laboratory data (e.g., sequence data) for public health surveillance. A participant described the experienced legal challenges by hospitals in the following example:

“GDPR, yes. The interpretation of that law is also very dependent on the lawyer who looks at it or the institute where you work. Of course, that's all complicated. It [privacy issues] is maybe an even bigger threat, soon with AI, than the lack of support. We do monitor and share data on infectious diseases, but it has now gone so far that, for example, for healthcare evaluation, where the law simply states that this is allowed, that some lawyers still say: “don't do it.” That's an issue.” (participant 13)

In addition, there also seems to be a lack of knowledge or expertise in hospitals on what is allowed under the GDPR regarding data sharing for public health in case of infectious disease outbreak, as one participant explained:

“[...] To what extent are you allowed to exchange data according to the GDPR? So far no one can tell me that, except, “[phew], very difficult” and “I don't know if it's allowed”.” (participant 4)

Insufficient resources and capacity

An important barrier in infectious disease surveillance in hospitals is related to insufficient information and communications technology (ICT) capacity:

“So, more people in the team, or more ICT people in such a team are needed, [...] That is really the bottleneck often when things don't get off the ground. And that applies to me with my team, but I also think that all other parties that work with surveillance data, and automate it or generate overviews, simply [rely] on ICT capacity.” (participant 2).

According to several participants, ICT personnel are needed who also have a good understanding of the medical issues at hand. Ideally, they could assist medical staff in translating problems encountered in daily clinical care into ICT solutions. In the setting of limited ICT capacity and funding in many hospitals, prioritization of projects by decision-makers in hospitals becomes inevitable. Top-down prioritization within a hospital of infectious disease surveillance would then be beneficial according to some participants. A participant explains why an operational SARI surveillance system has not been established in their hospital yet:

“But also the priorities and workload in the ICT department mean that, I think, it has not yet been successful. So that's workload, but also prioritization. If it was considered important enough, I think it might have been possible sooner.” (participant 6)

Facilitators

Clinically relevant and actionable data

A prominent theme regarding challenges in infectious disease surveillance in hospitals was related to clinical relevance of these hospital surveillance activities ([Supplementary material 3](#), Table 2). Willingness to participate in infectious disease surveillance seemed related to whether the collected data was seen as clinically relevant and actionable enough for patient care to have added value for hospitals, which was seen as having direct consequences for medical treatment and/or medical policy in hospitalized patients. In this context, many participants expressed that infectious disease surveillance in hospitals becomes worthwhile if it improves patient quality of care and/or facilitates healthcare innovation. The positive returns of establishing infectious disease surveillance in hospitals has become increasingly clear to participants in recent years, such as regional AMR surveillance in the following example:

“Because you continuously do surveillance, we can act very quickly when it comes to infection prevention, and the lines of communication are also extremely short. I do that for this hospital, but my colleagues do it for the other hospital and we can all view those results. As a result, there are few intermediate links.” (participant 4)

In the context of a demanding hospital setting with a high administrative burden and staff shortages, it was also regarded essential to have a critical attitude about data

requests by external stakeholders for infectious disease surveillance in hospitals in general, as was described by a participant:

“So, with every data source you ask for, I think you have to ask yourself: do I really need it? But also: where can you find these [data]? Is there already a standardization for this? And if not, then you really have to ask yourself whether that is something you should want to collect on a large scale in this phase, [...]” (participant 12)

Mutually beneficial collaboration

One of the most important facilitators for establishing robust infectious disease surveillance in hospitals appeared to be mutually beneficial collaboration with relevant stakeholders. For instance, a participant described the close collaboration between a large academic hospital and the regional municipal health service within the Amsterdam Regional Genomic epidemiology and Outbreak Surveillance (ARGOS) consortium as illustrative of the advantages of sharing surveillance data and expertise, which could lead to direct action on the regional or local level. Other long-term collaborations that have intensified between regional microbiology laboratories and hospitals since the COVID-19 pandemic are illustrated by one of the participants as follows, regarding respiratory pathogens, such as influenza and SARS-CoV-2:

“[...] And from this a regional assembly originated in which all medical microbiologists and infection prevention experts are represented, and more and more regional policy decisions are being made. So, the great thing about that is: you share information, you share policy, and you also share in decisions, and I think that is very powerful and very nice that it has come about that way. That is also getting better and better.” (participant 9)

Sufficient support

A sufficient degree of support was described as valuable for facilitating robust and sustainable infectious disease surveillance in hospitals. This support was required on multiple levels, ranging from supportive legislation and expertise, a blueprint for implementing hospital surveillance, sufficient funding for diagnostics with a public health aim, to prioritization by both the medical staff and the medical board. With regard to the preferred support, several participants noted that mandatory infectious disease in hospitals, excluding the already notifiable diseases, is not regarded as useful, but a (legal) framework defining roles and responsibilities is.

Recommendations

The participants described strategies on how the most important challenges could be faced to establish or maintain robust infectious disease surveillance in hospitals, and on how to create added value from the hospital perspective.

Establish roles and responsibilities of stakeholders

A common notion was that the objectives, roles, and responsibilities in infectious disease surveillance in hospitals that have a broader public health scope must be clarified to create a shared vision. A first step that a participant suggested is to have open discussions about it with the most relevant stakeholders in hospital surveillance with a public health scope from multiple levels:

"[...] So perhaps, the solution is to look at this in a more nuanced way. What are the objectives of those types of surveillance, and can we simply explain it more clearly to each other and have a dialogue about it?" (participant 11)

In addition, several participants recommend that guidance from the Dutch Ministry of Health is also required to establish the (legal) framework for achieving sustainable infectious disease surveillance in hospitals.

"Frameworks. Look, you just have to indicate that there are also a number of stakeholders who have to find solutions together within certain frameworks. And those frameworks must be set. All from the same money, I always think. Not an easy process, but I think [it is] one that needs to be managed if you want to get out of this. Certainly, also for the future." (participant 11)

Ensure actionable data with clinical relevance for hospital patient care

In general, it was emphasized to focus on obtaining *actionable* surveillance data from the hospital perspective, i.e., with impact on patient clinical care to ensure the sustainability of infectious disease surveillance in hospitals. The most often cited key attributes of these hospital surveillance systems were 'timeliness' and 'flexibility.' According to participants, the required timeliness differs for specific infectious disease syndromes or pathogens under surveillance, ranging from (near) real-time to monthly to quarterly to half-yearly. Additionally, it is dependent on the surveillance objective set by the hospital and/or the current epidemiological situation. In general, the value of sufficient timely hospital surveillance data was expressed as follows:

"It is of course information for action. So, you don't want to find out only a year later that there was a problem a year ago. So, timeliness is very important." (participant 2)

The flexibility of surveillance systems was also regarded as an important attribute as the hospitals expressed a strong need to swiftly adapt to changing information needs. Adaptively upscaling or downscaling surveillance activities depending on a changing epidemiological situation was perceived as a requirement, especially in the setting of hospital outbreaks. In this context, a clear preference was expressed for routinely and continuously regional infectious disease surveillance data in addition to national infectious disease data:

"For the future it is super important to know - not only in the province, but maybe even in a part of the province - where is your problem? In which village or which...? And that you can really... As long as you can share that data with each other, you can really map it out fantastically and take specific measures." (participant 9).

From the perspective of hospitals, having insight into infectious disease surveillance outputs on the regional level is regarded as highly beneficial, because it provides actionable data for *their* own catchment population. Especially, since regional transfers of patients occur frequently between hospitals in the Netherlands, insight into transmission dynamics on the regional level is regarded of the utmost importance. Participants elaborated on numerous initiatives (e.g., ARGOS, AMR Healthcare Networks) undertaken on the regional level by collaborating hospitals, microbiological laboratories and/or municipal health services to facilitate this need.

Benefit from the innovative qualities of hospitals

Several participants saw opportunities for establishing robust infectious disease surveillance in hospitals with a wider public health scope. One participant advised to benefit broadly from the innovative power of academic hospitals, ranging from utilizing their crosslinked networks, spin-off private companies, technological innovations, such as artificial intelligence, to their extensive expertise with complex patient groups:

"And I think you also should really use the innovative power of the University Medical Centers in the field of infectious diseases. That is where the University Medical Centers really have their added value. [...]" (participant 11).

This innovative power of clinical microbiological laboratories was also underlined by another participant:

“If we want to have a system in which we can respond quickly to outbreaks, then you will need a system that embraces technological innovations. And that can actually be incorporated into the whole of how techniques, lab options, those developments are used in the microbiological world, so that they are immediately passed on throughout the chain.” (participant 14)

Discussion

To identify common grounds between stakeholders, such as clinical staff from hospitals and/or laboratories, and public health institutes, it is essential that their different perspectives on the wants, needs, and requirements of hospital surveillance are recognized. To our knowledge, this qualitative research is one of the few recent studies [8, 9] since the end of the COVID-19 pandemic that provides insight on the barriers, facilitators, and preferred requirements of infectious disease surveillance from the perspective of Dutch hospitals. Within the hospital setting, this qualitative research indicated that there are nuanced differences in the perspectives on hospital surveillance depending on the aim of the syndrome/disease/pathogen under surveillance and stakeholder type. Based on the semi-structured interview results, we provide practical recommendations that might help to find common grounds between relevant stakeholders to facilitate robust and sustainable hospital surveillance in the Netherlands.

The three main recommendations for maintaining or establishing robust and sustainable hospital surveillance are: i) ensure clinically relevant actionable data; ii) clarify roles and responsibilities; and iii) collaborate on innovative initiatives. Firstly, we recommend public health institutes in collaboration with hospitals to focus on clinically relevant actionable data from the perspective of hospitals when establishing infectious disease surveillance. This will likely result in improved intrinsic motivation of hospitals to participate in infectious disease surveillance activities and ensure long-term sustainability of the surveillance system. Hereby, it is also essential to provide timely mirror data for feedback or benchmarking on a user-friendly, easy-accessible platform to facilitate the reporting of these surveillance data to hospital staff. In addition, the added value of these surveillance results for hospitals would be increased if the geographical scale of the mirror data is adjustable according to the hospital needs (e.g., local/regional/national level). This would fulfill the need of many hospitals to adjust mirror data to regional level, which provides them with the most clinically relevant actionable data.

Secondly, we recommend defining the roles and responsibilities of key stakeholders in hospital surveillance more clearly and collaboratively, especially regarding hospital surveillance with a broader public health aim. Currently, some hospitals seem unaware or do not acknowledge their own distinct role in a routine and continuous infectious

disease surveillance in hospitals with a broader public health scope. A way forward could be to first set up informal meetings or round tables with key stakeholders to discuss surveillance objectives, needs and requirements of infectious disease surveillance systems in hospitals. This could lead to more insight into each other's needs, further exploration of common grounds, and fine-tuning of a blueprint for sustainable SARI surveillance in the Netherlands. This process is already ongoing with a project in collaboration with Dutch Hospital Data (DHD), RIVM, the Netherlands Federation of University Medical Centers (NFU), the Dutch Hospitals Association (NVZ) to establish SARI surveillance using financial claim codes and laboratory data. As several hospitals experienced the lack of a (legal) framework that could facilitate more clearly defined public health roles, it would be helpful to clarify the role of hospitals in the current adjustment of the Public Health Act (Wpg) in the Netherlands [10]. Providing a framework would help hospitals commit to public health tasks to a greater extent, acknowledge their responsibility, and contribute to providing baseline infectious disease data on hospital level. It would also raise the awareness in hospitals that routinely and continuously collected infectious disease surveillance data, are essential for adequate and timely detection of infectious disease outbreaks in hospitals.

Thirdly, it is recommended to public health institutes to benefit from the innovative qualities of hospitals and microbiology laboratories by creating long-term, mutually beneficial collaborations with hospitals for establishing robust infectious disease surveillance. Mutually beneficial collaboration between these stakeholders could lie in technological innovations, such as the implementations of artificial intelligence technologies, which could be of added value for both infectious disease surveillance and improving quality of patientcare. In addition, hospital surveillance data could be regarded as a valuable data source for innovative, clinically relevant research or for addressing policy questions in the field of infectious disease. The extensive innovation of hospital microbiological laboratories regarding whole-genomic sequencing was also recommended to be embraced by all stakeholders in the chain to fully utilize its potential.

This qualitative research has several strengths and limitations to consider. A general strength of the purposive sampling method is that it is an efficient way to select participants who are likely to contribute comprehensively and share diverse insights, because of their knowledge or experience with the topic [11, 12]. This can benefit the quality and accuracy of research findings [12, 13]. However, the level of knowledge and experience of participants with the topic in the current study was sometimes limited to general needs or possibilities within a medical specialty and did not always extend to specific knowledge about surveillance or potential surveillance systems. Yet, this could also be perceived as an important outcome of the current research, which informs

future course of action with different stakeholders. Another potential limitation regarding purposive sampling is the potential influence of the researcher on the sampling process, leading to a biased sample [11]. However, this is likely to be limited because the sampling method was reinforced by the formal stakeholder analysis to identify as many relevant stakeholders as possible. Lastly, the group of participants did not include pulmonary medical specialists due to nonresponse. However, despite this limitation, we believe this study managed to capture the most relevant views and identify common themes in most relevant key stakeholders with high power/interest, because sufficient data saturation occurred to allow drawing conclusions from the thematic analysis.

Conclusions

This qualitative research provides new insights in the experienced barriers and facilitators for infectious diseases surveillance in Dutch hospitals from the hospital perspective since the end of the COVID-19 pandemic. Based on input from key stakeholders in the hospital setting, this study provides practical recommendations that can be of added value for improving robust and sustainable infectious disease surveillance in Dutch hospitals in the future.

List of abbreviations

AMR: antimicrobial resistance; DHD: Dutch Hospital Data; GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation; ICU: intensive care unit; ICT: information and communications technology; NFU: Netherlands Federation of University Medical Centers; NVZ: Dutch Hospitals Association; RIVM: National Institute for Public Health and the Environment; RSV: respiratory syncytial virus; SARI: severe acute respiratory infections; Wpg: Public Health Act in the Netherlands

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

The Dutch Medical Research Involving Human Subjects Act (Dutch acronym: WMO) did not apply to this study, because only fully anonymous data were used and there were no interventions.

Consent for publication

All participants of the semi-structured interviews gave consent for publication of the results of this qualitative research.

Availability of data and material

The datasets used and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Competing interests

The authors declare they have no competing interests.

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Authors' contributions

Sierk Marbus (SDM) designed the study, analysed and interpreted the data, and drafted the manuscript. Tjarda Boere (TB) designed the study, analysed and interpreted the data, reviewed and edited the manuscript. Irene Veldhuijzen co-designed the semi-structured interview guide and reviewed the manuscript. Rianne van Gageldonk-Lafeber co-designed the semi-structured interview guide and reviewed the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Supplementary material 2.

Semi-structured interview guide

General:

- Do you give permission for this conversation to be recorded?
- Would you briefly introduce yourself? (name, position, hospital/long-term care facility/institute)
- What is the most important reason(s) for you to participate in this interview?
- How would you define hospital surveillance?
 - *Follow-up remarks:*
 - Explanation of how the RIVM defines hospital surveillance, and what the legal tasks of the RIVM are in the field of infectious disease surveillance
 - Explanation that the scope of this interview is limited to *infectious disease*-related topics within hospital surveillance.

Current practice and barriers to surveillance of infectious diseases in the hospital:

1. Which infectious disease monitoring and/or registration systems are currently operational in your hospital and/or does your hospital contribute to?
 - *Potential follow-up question:*
 - a) Could you describe these operational infectious disease surveillance systems?
2. What kind of information do you think is most relevant for your hospital? And why?
 - *Potential follow-up questions:*
 - a. With what frequency is this data available for your hospital?
 - b. How current are these data?
 - c. How do you estimate the data quality from this surveillance system? (By data quality we mean the completeness and validity of the data)
 - d. How sustainable do you think this operational surveillance system for infectious diseases is? (By a sustainable surveillance system we mean a surveillance system in which long-term maintenance and support of routinely obtained data is guaranteed during times of crisis and beyond)
 - e. Are there specific infectious syndromes and/or pathogens that you would like to monitor within your hospital?
3. What are the barriers you encounter in establishing and/or maintaining an infectious disease surveillance system in your hospital?
 - *Potential follow-up questions:*
 - a. Which barrier(s) is/are most important? And why?
 - b. How do you think these barrier(s) can be resolved?
 - c. What role do you see for your hospital/care facility in this?
 - d. What role do you see for other stakeholders in this?

Available hospital data of infectious diseases:

4. What data (sources/sets/standards) are already available in your hospital that could potentially be used for a future surveillance system of infectious diseases?
 - *Potential follow-up questions:*
 - a. With what frequency is this data available to your hospital?
 - b. How current are these data?
 - c. If this data is not yet used, what do you think the reason is?
 - d. To what extent does your hospital/care facility have supporting technical staff (ICT specialists/data managers) to facilitate this?

Wishes and requirements for hospital surveillance of infectious diseases according to stakeholder:

5. What requirements do you think an infectious diseases monitoring system must meet to be of added value to your hospital?

➤ *Potential follow-up questions:*

Potential introduction:

Certain conditions for hospital surveillance are important to the RIVM, partly because of its legal task in the context of public health. The following topics address some of these conditions, as we are interested in the extent to which these conditions are relevant to you or your hospital.

- a. If 4c is answered affirmatively: what does your hospital need, in order to make this possible?
 - b. With which frequency should data be available to the hospital? And why?
 - c. How current does the data need to be for this? What is the reason for that?
 - d. To what extent should the surveillance system be automated? And why?
 - e. How important do you think data quality is for a surveillance system?
 - f. How important do you think the sustainability of a surveillance system is? Can you explain why?
 - g. To what extent do you think it is important that available outcomes for your hospital can be shared internally and/or externally? What is the reason for this?
 - h. What could be the role of your hospital/care facility in achieving these wishes?
 - i. What could be the role of other stakeholders in achieving these wishes?
6. Is there anything else you would like to come back to or any other point you would like to raise?

Appendix 3. Blueprint severe acute respiratory surveillance in the Netherlands

Background

The National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) conducts surveillance of respiratory infections on behalf of the Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport (VWS) in the Netherlands. Effective surveillance requires insight into the different layers of the surveillance pyramid ([Figure 2](#)). The lower layers of the surveillance pyramid concern the spread of respiratory infections in the general population (with or without symptoms), while the higher layers involve patients who either visit their general practitioner, are being hospitalized, or pass away as a result of an acute respiratory infection. Only total mortality is promptly available through the Central Statistical Office (CBS); cause-specific mortality has months of delay and is also incomplete for acute respiratory infections. Data on general practitioner visits are available through Netherlands Institute for Health Services Research (Nivel), but timely insight into acute respiratory infections requiring hospitalization (a.k.a. severe acute respiratory infections, or SARI) is lacking. Signals can come from different surveillance sources within different layers of the surveillance pyramid at various times and must therefore be interpreted in their specific context.

The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic stressed the importance of hospital data for monitoring severe infections and assessing the severity of infections by estimating the proportion of severe infections. A specific COVID-19 hospital registration was set-up ad hoc in 2020 and has since been discontinued. The importance of SARI surveillance for structural and timely insight into respiratory infections requiring hospitalization, thus with broader scope than COVID-19, became apparent more recently. In 2023, an increase in pneumonia cases among children and adolescents was detected in Nivel's general practitioner surveillance, but the severity of this increase could not be assessed due to the lack of data on severe infections requiring hospitalization. For structural and timely insight into SARI, a sustainable data flow from hospitals to the RIVM is needed. This blueprint describes the objectives of SARI surveillance, the set-up of the two data streams currently being developed for this purpose, and the status and planning of both projects in the Netherlands. This is followed by a discussion and various potential scenarios. Finally, we provide advice on the progress of SARI surveillance in the Netherlands.

Figure 2. Surveillance pyramid

Objectives of SARI surveillance

SARI data provide insight into severe acute respiratory infections requiring hospitalization. This complements surveillance data such as wastewater analysis, the number of self-reported respiratory infections (Infectieradar), and general practitioner visits for respiratory infections (Nivel). Surveillance data are essential for monitoring trends and detecting surges of disease incidence, where the timeliness of the data is crucial to potentially take targeted measures to combat an outbreak or surge. Early detection of unexpected and/or regional increases in known respiratory infections, as well as emerging infectious diseases, contributes to pandemic preparedness. SARI data provide insight into the proportion of severe infections and are important for determining the burden of respiratory infections. Additionally, data on SARI patients are important for evaluating control measures aimed at preventing severe illness and death, and overwhelming of the healthcare system, and they are a key input for modelling the effects of healthcare intervention measures. Finally, countries are advised by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) to establish a SARI surveillance system and are requested to provide data from it for the international surveillance of respiratory infections. The European Union (EU) regulation on serious cross-border health threats includes a list of communicable diseases and related special health issues that must be covered by epidemiological surveillance. Approval for adding SARI to this list is expected by the end of 2024. In summary, the objectives of SARI surveillance are:

1. Early detection and monitoring of trends of severe acute respiratory infections and their pathogens in:
 - a. time: weekly

- b. place: regional differences
 - c. person: individuals at increased risk of severe infections
 2. Contributing to determining the burden of acute respiratory infections
 3. In-depth analysis based on patient characteristics for:
 - a. identifying risk groups
 - b. determining the impact of vaccination programs (vaccine effectiveness) and evaluating other healthcare measures, if necessary

SARI surveillance system

For effective SARI-surveillance, it is important that the data is timely, complete, and representative, and also contains relevant patient characteristics. At the same time, the registration burden for hospitals should be minimized, and traceability to individual patients should be prevented. For hospitals, automated data submission will lead to less administrative burden than manual data submission. An automated data flow better ensures the timeliness and completeness of the data. In addition to automated data submission from hospitals to a central database, the processing and analysis of the data should also be as automated as much as possible to timely interpret trends. An automated data flow that continues even during quiet (non-epidemic) times is important, because it ensures the system is "activated" during a surge. Furthermore, data over a longer period is essential to assess trends and the extent of a surge in disease incidence.

The Netherlands currently does not have a structural and real-time view of SARI. The RIVM has initiated two projects for SARI-surveillance. The goal is to establish robust near real-time automated data flows on SARI patients from hospitals to the RIVM. Near real-time means weekly submission to the RIVM, which can be upscaled to daily (real-time) during a pandemic outbreak if necessary. The set-up of both projects as intended is described under A and B. Subsequently, the status and planning per dataflow ([A](#) and [B](#)) are described to what extent the intended setup has been realized.

A. SARI in intensive care units using the National Intensive Care Evaluation Foundation registry

- In 2022, this project started in collaboration with the National Intensive Care Evaluation Foundation (NICE). The NICE registry is an existing quality-of-care registry in which all Dutch ICUs participate.

- To identify SARI patients, ICU admission diagnoses are determined by the intensivist (APACHE-IV codes), recorded in the electronic patient record (EPR) and subsequently routinely collected in the NICE registry. Since 2023, there are also specific APACHE-IV codes for infections with influenza virus, SARS-CoV-2, and respiratory syncytial virus (RSV).
- The project automates data delivery from hospitals to NICE and improves the timeliness of data delivery at a daily frequency. This required a technical investment in which NICE receives hospital data using the HL7-FHIR standard (FHIR) for data exchange, transfer of the NICE database to the cloud, and make adjustments by the EPR suppliers. Contracts between NICE and the hospitals also had to be revised due to data storage in the cloud.
- The NICE registry includes all individual admissions to adult ICUs, but pediatric ICUs (PICUs) are not included.
- The weekly data flow from NICE to RIVM will contain aggregated data on all ICU admissions for SARI (if desired, this can be switched to case-based data, in pseudonymized form, with less information (fewer variables and/or subgroups) than in the aggregated data).
- Available patient characteristics: admission week, syndrome based on a selection of diagnosis codes (see [supplementary material 3](#) for SARI syndrome), as well as individual diagnoses, gender, age group (n=7), province, comorbidity (main risk groups), in-ICU mortality, medical ward in-patient mortality, and time from ICU admission to death.

B. SARI in wards and intensive care units using Dutch Hospital Data

- This project started at the end of 2023 in collaboration with the Dutch Hospital Data Foundation (DHD). DHD manages the National Basic Registration of Hospital Care (LBZ) for which all Dutch hospitals provide data.
- The Dutch Association of Hospitals (NVZ) and the Dutch Federation of University Medical Centers (NFU) support the project, and a cooperation agreement between RIVM-NVZ-NFU has been signed.
- To identify SARI patients, the following will be used:
 - Diagnosis Treatment Combination (DBC) codes for the financial claim assessment of the care request upon admission.
 - Requests for laboratory tests for SARI-related pathogens (e.g. influenza virus, RSV, SARS-CoV-2, and pneumococci) as an indication of suspected SARI.

- A separate SARI registry is being set-up at DHD because the existing LBZ registry is not timely enough and does not contain laboratory data. For the weekly data delivery from hospitals to DHD, a link is made between admission and laboratory test request information from the EPR and available test result data in the laboratory information system.
- The SARI registry obtains data from all hospitalized patients, but only includes admissions that meet the inclusion criteria (SARI-related DBC code and/or SARI-related laboratory request).
- The data flow from DHD to RIVM contains individual patient data (case-based) in a pseudonymized form that is not traceable to the individual patient or hospital. Additionally, every two months, DHD will add medical diagnosis codes (ICD-10) from the LBZ registry to the data received by RIVM for validation purposes.
- Available patient characteristics are: admission week, DBC code (see supplementary material 3 for SARI syndrome definitions), gender, age (years), safety region/province, ICU admission (yes/no), isolation, laboratory request, laboratory result.

See [supplementary material 3](#) for a summary table of the setup of both data flows. See [supplementary material 4](#), for SARI case definitions used for the NICE data ([APACHE diagnosis codes](#)) and for the DHD data ([DBC codes](#)).

Current state of affairs on 1st September 2024 and planning

A. SARI in ICUs using the NICE registry

- The technical investments have largely been made from mid-2022 up to October 2024.
 - Development of a module at NICE for incoming data from hospitals using Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) server
 - Establishment of a NICE Database in the cloud. External security tests (for data security) are scheduled for Q3 and Q4 2024
 - The most commonly used EPR systems (Itémedical, Chipsoft, and EPIC) are prepared for automatic data delivery using FHIR
 - The automatic transfer of SARI data from NICE to the RIVM is in an advanced stage. The delivery of test data to the RIVM will be tested in Q3 and Q4 2024.
- Retrospective data (2016-2023) has been provided by NICE to the RIVM for validation research and in preparation for weekly reporting by the RIVM.

- It is expected that the delivery of SARI data to the RIVM will start in Q4 2024. This can start once data processing by NICE is ready for at least 2-3 ICUs (in order to ensure the anonymity of the ICUs).
- A data pipeline for weekly reporting has been built by the RIVM. Real-time testing and further fine-tuning are planned for Q3 and Q4 2024.
- By the end of December 2024, 20 to 29 ICUs will be connected and delivering data (from the three different EPR systems: Itémedical, Chipsoft, and EPIC).
- It is expected that by 2025, all ICUs using the previously mentioned EPR systems (approximately 95% of all Dutch ICUs) will be connected.
- An additional explanation of the ICU data from NICE is attached as appendix 1 to this blueprint.

B. SARI in wards and ICUs using DHD

- Technical preparations on the part of DHD are complete to receive, process, and deliver data from hospitals to the RIVM.
- The willingness to participate among hospitals was investigated through a survey, after which hospitals were individually approached to discuss the terms of participation.
- Eight hospitals have indicated they can connect in 2024, three of which have started preparations, and five hospitals have stated that sufficient internal technical capacity must be available to meet the schedule.
- Fourteen hospitals indicate they can connect in 2025, under various conditions. The mentioned conditions include certainty about the continuation of the project, the realization of automatic extraction by the EPR supplier, and sufficient available capacity and funding.
- Two hospitals have indicated they need a clear understanding of the required time and budget before committing to a connection timeline.
- DHD expects 19 hospitals to connect, although these hospitals have not explicitly indicated this and have not provided a timeline. However, the hospitals have listed conditions for participation.
- Four hospitals have indicated to DHD that they will not connect.

- For 22 hospitals, there has been no renewed contact by DHD, or ongoing contact has not led to clarity about whether or when they will connect. Therefore, there is no certainty about whether, and if so when, these 22 hospitals will connect.
- DHD has indicated that extracting information from the laboratory system will be a challenge because not all hospitals have a lab system within the EPR. To keep the connection process accessible, providing laboratory results are not initially mandatory. However, this information would be of significant added value for SARI surveillance using DHD. It is therefore important to quickly clarify whether full connection, including lab data, is possible, on what timeline, and what the implications are. Two of the three hospitals currently setting up the connection will also provide lab data. The timeline for including test results for the third hospital in the data flow is unclear yet.
- It is expected that in 2025 only sentinel surveillance will be possible based on data from a limited number of hospitals. To ensure representativeness, it is necessary to connect at least one hospital from each safety region and to have a reflection of both general and academic hospitals, taking into account the distribution of the population per region and the size of the hospital. It is unclear yet whether and, if so, on what timeline this could be realized.
- The update report from DHD and an addendum to the update are attached as appendices 2 and 3 to this blueprint.

Considerations based on current state of affairs

Based on the current status, it is not possible to make a statement about data completeness and representativeness, as the number of connected hospitals for both data streams are too limited. Therefore, there is currently no real-time SARI data to analyze. It is expected that in the course of 2025, SARI data will be received from the majority of ICUs using the NICE registry data flow. Since not all hospitals are expected to be connected to the data stream using DHD in 2025, initial insights into SARI in wards will be as if it were a sentinel surveillance system with a limited number of hospitals. The limitation of a sentinel system is that the population from which the patients originate cannot be accurately determined because the catchment areas of the hospitals overlap. As a result, the incidence of hospital admissions (overall and by age) cannot be calculated. However, based on historical data from the national registration of hospital admissions (LBZ registration), it can be assessed what proportion of admissions in a given period was recorded by the hospitals that provide data for SARI surveillance. This proportion can be used to extrapolate the number of hospital admissions to an expected national number with an upper and lower limit. The unreliability of data on

hospital admissions increases with a limited number of participating hospitals, especially with low incidence and few admissions. Therefore, the focus is on national coverage and connecting the remaining hospitals in 2026.

When both data streams are operational and the RIVM has sufficient data (expected in 2026), the RIVM will conduct an evaluation to determine whether both data streams are necessary for a representative SARI surveillance in the Netherlands. This will also determine the value of SARI surveillance based on hospital and intensive care data in relation to the existing respiratory surveillance. This aligns with the Programme on innovating and strengthening infectious disease surveillance RIVM.

Scenarios

Scenario 1 – Continue with only the data flow from ICUs using the NICE registry

- **Advantage:** Investments for adapting the EPR systems have been made, and the implementation phase has started. There is almost a data stream ready that can provide a near-complete picture of ICU admissions, because it is derived from the existing NICE registry in which all ICUs participate. This provides insight into the most severe SARI cases requiring ICU admission.
- **Disadvantage:** ICU admissions represent the "tip of the iceberg" of SARI, despite being an important layer in the surveillance pyramid and ICU capacity is regarded as the first bottleneck in a severe outbreak. With only insight into the ICUs, the contribution to pandemic preparedness is limited, and it cannot or only to a limited extent contribute to SARI surveillance at European level.

Scenario 2 – Continue with only DHD

- **Advantage:** Ward admissions provide a more complete picture of SARI admissions, and EPR data linked to laboratory results allow for better interpretation of SARI.
- **Disadvantage:** Investments are still needed in 2025 to connect hospitals. Stopping the data stream from ICUs using the NICE registry has the disadvantage that there is no complete picture of ICU admissions, and the potential added value of monitoring other syndromes than SARI is not utilized. A risk of this scenario is that if the data stream using DHD fails, we are back to square one and have no SARI surveillance at all. DHD has expressed the expectation that retrieving laboratory test results will be a challenge for some hospitals. It should also be noted that there is currently no clarity about participation from 22 hospitals (32%). The RIVM has no influence on this matter due to the inability to communicate directly with these hospitals.

Scenario 3 – Continue with both NICE and DHD for the time being, so it can be investigated how much the two systems complement each other or if one of the two systems is sufficient (it is too early to determine this now).

- **Advantage:** Continuing with both data streams, combines the advantages mentioned in scenarios 1 and 2, providing a more complete picture of SARI in wards and ICUs. This strengthens the pandemic preparedness of the Netherlands. Additionally, by sharing this data, we contribute to SARI surveillance on European level.
- **Disadvantage:** as described in scenario 2, investments are still required in 2025 to connect hospitals to the data stream using DHD. As mentioned in scenario 2, there is a risk that the condition to include laboratory test results may not be fully met, and there is uncertainty about the participation of approximately one-third of the hospitals.

Advice

Our recommendation is to select scenario 3: continue with the implementation of both data streams and move towards a maintenance phase. If both data streams are realized as planned in 2025, an evaluation will be conducted in 2026 to determine where they are complementary and where they overlap, and to assess whether it is necessary to maintain both data streams long term. We expect to have SARI surveillance operational using both data streams in 2025.

Supplementary material 3.

Table S1. Data streams

	Hospitals (DHD)	ICUs (NICE)	Comments
Population	General population	General adult population	Pediatric Intensive Care Units (PICUs) are not included in the NICE registry
System design	Automated	Automated	
Hospital type	General wards and ICUs of academic and general hospitals	ICUs of academic and general hospitals	
Number of hospitals	70	70	This is the total number of general- and academic hospitals in the Netherlands relevant for SARI
Legal status	Voluntary	Voluntary	NICE is a quality-of-care registry
Level of data	Case-based	Aggregated	
Aggregation in time	Calendar week of admission	Calendar week of admission	
Frequency	Weekly	Weekly	Scalable to daily (DHD) and multiple times per day (NICE) in case of a pandemic
Retrospective data	Yes, complete data available from 2014 for syndromes derived from the National Basic Registration Hospital Care (LBZ). Possibly limited microbiological data available.	Yes, complete data available from 2012 on with full coverage by all adult ICUs	NICE data is also available before 2012, but with incomplete coverage.
SARI case definition	Based on selection of financial claim codes (DBC) related	Based on selection of APACHE codes related to SARI.	For SARI, broad and narrow definitions are defined based

	to the SARI syndrome. These financial claim codes are registered at admission and can be adjusted after.	APACHE codes are registered at ICU admission.	on both financial claim codes and APACHE codes
SARI case definition microbiological test request	4 pathogens (influenza, RSV, SARS-CoV-2, and pneumococci)	Not applicable	
Microbiological test result	4 pathogens (influenza, RSV, SARS-CoV-2, and pneumococci). Possibly scalable in case of outbreak.	Since 2024: if influenza, RSV, or SARS-CoV-2 is laboratory-confirmed, this is processed in the APACHE diagnosis code	In NICE, a positive lab result is included in the APACHE diagnosis code. DHD data will be a combination of EPR and Laboratory Information Management System
ICU admission	Yes (yes/no)	Yes (ICU admission diagnosis)	
Mortality	No	Yes	
Patient characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Age in years (<2 years: in months) -Sex -Safety Region -Isolation measures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Age (7 age categories, adjustable) -Sex -Region & province -Comorbidities -Mechanical ventilation -In-ICU mortality -Post-ICU in-hospital mortality -Time-to-death on ICU or general ward - Length of ICU stay and length of hospital stay 	

Supplementary material 4.

SARI case definitions

Intensive care unit, based on APACHE codes:

1) SARI Probable:

- Influenza
- Pneumonia, bacterial
- Pneumonia, fungal
- Pneumonia, other
- Pneumonia, parasitic (i.e. Pneumocystis pneumonia)
- Pneumonia, viral
- Respiratory Syncytial Virus (RSV) infection
- SARS-CoV-2 infection
- Sepsis, pulmonary

2) SARI Possible:

- ARDS-adult respiratory distress syndrome, non-cardiogenic pulmonary edema
- Atelectasis
- Chest pain, respiratory
- Chest pain, unknown origin
- Effusions, pleural
- Hemorrhage/hemoptysis, pulmonary

General ward, based on financial claim codes

Table S2: SARI-specific financial claim (DBC) codes (adults)

Medical specialty-code	Diagnosis-code	Medical specialty	Diagnosis	Broad / Narrow
0313	007	Internal medicine	Analysis dyspnea without diagnosis	B
0313	015	Internal medicine	Analysis fever without diagnosis	B
0313	401	Internal medicine	Pneumonia not further specified	N
0313	402	Internal medicine	Interstitial pneumonia	N
0313	409	Internal medicine	Other respiratory infection not further specified	N
0313	431	Internal medicine	Bacteremia/sepsis	B
0313	469	Internal medicine	Other viral infection not further specified	N
0322	1401	Pulmonology	Pneumonia	N

0322	1405	Pulmonology	Acute (trachea)bronchitis	B
0322	1241	Pulmonology	COPD	B
0335	271	Geriatrics	Respiratory tract disorders	B
0335	272	Geriatrics	COPD	B
0335	273	Geriatrics	Pneumonia	N
0335	101	Geriatrics	Multiple organ disorders	B

Table S3: SARI-specific financial claim codes (children)

Medical specialty-code	Diagnosis-code	Medical specialty	Diagnosis	Broad / Narrow
0316	3104	Pediatrics	Upper respiratory infection	N
0316	3208	Pediatrics	Lower respiratory infection	N
0316	3210	Pediatrics	RSV-bronchiolitis	N
0316	3202	Pediatrics	Asthma/bronchial hyperreactivity	B
0316	8910	Pediatrics	Fever of unknown origin	B
0316	7810	Pediatrics	Viral infection/viremia not further specified	B
0316	3105	Pediatrics	Laryngitis subglottica	N

Appendix 4. Retrospective analysis of ICU data for other syndromes than SARI

Figure 3. Five-week moving average number of gastro admissions in Dutch intensive care units (2016-2023)

* Aggregated ICU data based on APACHE-IV diagnosis codes reflecting the gastro syndrome are used.